

The Condensation of Chloral with *m*-Cresotic Acid.

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The condensation of chloral (a) with *m*-cresotic acid has been studied by Alimchandani and Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 201; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 1) and by Schleussner and Voswinckel (*Annalen*, 1921, 422, 111); (b) with the methyl ether of *m*-cresotic acid by Meldrum and Alimchandani (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 253).

The condensation product, when *m*-cresotic acid is used, is a complex mixture. Hence Meldrum and Alimchandani attempted to simplify matters by working with the methyl ether of the acid. The result was the production of evidence that chloral condenses with the benzene nucleus in the *para*-position to the methoxy group: α -coccinic acid (V) was obtained from its methyl ether as the ultimate product.

α -Coccinic acid.

γ -Coccinic acid.

Schleussner and Voswinckel found that chloral condenses with *m*-cresotic acid in the *meta*-position to the hydroxy group: they obtained, as ultimate products, γ -coccinic acid and its methyl ether, the latter agreeing in melting point with the methyl ether obtained by Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1712).

We have made an intensive study of the condensation of chloral with *m*-cresotic acid, with a view to ascertain the structure of the different products. We find that chloral condenses in the *para*-position to the hydroxy group as Meldrum and Alimchandani found with the methyl ether.

It has been possible to isolate three crystalline substances from the condensation product of chloral with *m*-cresotic acid: (a) 4-hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzene (I), (b) the lactone of that substance (II), and (c) 4-hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl- α -hydroxy- $\omega\omega$ -dichlorostyrene (III).

The question had to be settled where the linking of the chloral molecule takes place. The substance (I) on hydrolysis yielded a substituted mandelic acid (IV) which on oxidation gave α -coccinic acid (V) identical with that obtained by Meldrum and Alimchandani on hydrolysis of the methyl ether (1929, *loc. cit.*). The same acid was obtained directly by the oxidation of the substance (I).

Further, the substance (I) on reduction with zinc and acetic acid gave 2-methyl-5-carboxy-4-hydroxy-1- $\beta\beta$ -dichloroethylbenzene (VI), which on methylation was found to be identical with that of Meldrum and Alimchandani (1929, *loc. cit.*). The substance (VI) on treatment with sulphuric acid gave a phenylacetic acid (VII) which on methylation yielded the methyl ether of the phenylacetic acid identical with that of Meldrum and Alimchandani. The methyl derivative of the substance (VI) on treatment with sodium hydroxide gave the substance (VIII).

The substance (II) gives the same products as (I) on similar treatment: (a) the mandelic acid (IV) on hydrolysis, and (b) the product (VI) on reduction. The amount of the substance (II) obtained from the condensation mixture is small. It was found possible to prepare it in quantity from the substance (I) by heating at its melting point.

The formula (II) which is that of a β -lactone, may seem unlikely. However, any formula other than (II) for this lactone is excluded because the substance (i) does not give ferric chloride reaction, (ii) dissolves slowly in hot sodium hydroxide and (iii) gives a monoacetyl

derivative, which on reduction with zinc and acetic acid gives the product (VI) with elimination of the acetyl group.

The formation of the substance (III) depends on the elimination of a molecule of hydrochloric acid from the substance (I) (*cf.* Chattaway and Prats, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 685). The substance (III) on reduction gave the substance (IX) *i.e.*, $-\text{C}(\text{OH})\text{:CCl}_2$ was changed into $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$. On acetylation, the substance (III) gave a diacetyl derivative. All attempts to prepare a semicarbazide and a phenylhydrazone or an osazone were fruitless. Hence it tends to react mainly in the enolic form. Chattaway and Prats (*loc. cit.*) found that their substance showed keto-enolic isomerism.

All our condensation products contain the chloral molecule in the *para*-position to the hydroxyl group. Schleussner and Voswinckel (*loc. cit.*) found that condensation of chloral with *m*-cresotic acid takes place in the *meta*-position. In order to ascertain whether this difference is due to a difference in the concentration of the condensing agent (sulphuric acid) or to the higher temperature at which the reaction was carried out in India, or to both these causes, the condensation was tried under varying conditions:—

(a) Schleussner and Voswinckel's condensation was repeated by keeping the condensing mixture (i) for 24 hours and (ii) for 3 days in a refrigerator.

(b) The experiment was repeated, the condensing agent being 90 per cent. sulphuric acid.

In all cases, hydrolysis and oxidation of the condensation product led not to γ -coccinic acid but to α -coccinic acid.

Generally the indications are that the substances with which Schleussner and Voswinckel worked were not pure. This is due first to the fact that the complex condensation mixture is difficult to crystallise and second to the fact that instead of crystallising from an organic solvent, they treated the product by dissolving in dilute alkali and acidifying with hydrochloric acid. The resulting precipitate was then washed and dried at 105° , when it lost water and melted at about 300° . Their substance of the same empirical composition as (IV) is described by them as yellowish, m.p. 204° . The authors find that their crude substance is yellowish, m.p. $211\text{--}12^\circ$, and on purification by means of its barium salt becomes white, m.p. 227° .

Chattaway and Calvet (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 2914) have obtained from chloral and *p*-nitroanisole, as the sole product of reaction, a substance which contains the group $-\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$. Meldrum and

Alimchandani (*loc. cit.*) also got a substance with the same group in the condensation of the methyl ether of *m*-cresotic acid. A substance (X) containing the same group is obtained when hydrochloric acid gas is passed into the mixture of chloral, *m*-cresotic acid and sulphuric acid. For some purposes, the groups $-\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ and $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ are equivalent. The substance (X), on hydrolysis and on reduction gave respectively the products (IV) and (VI), which are got on similar treatment of the substance (I) containing the group $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CCl}_3$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzene (I)—*m*-Cresotic acid (10 g.), chloral hydrate (11 g.) and sulphuric acid (97-98 per cent, 50 c.c.) were mixed and the materials formed a clear solution on shaking. On the third day, the mixture was poured over ice; a solid separated which was collected, washed with hot water and dried in an air-oven at 90° (yield, 12 g.). The crude product (A) was worked up separately (see below).

The filtrate was evaporated on the hot air-bath when needle-shaped crystals of the substance (I) were obtained (4 g.) which were found to effloresce. It was crystallised from a mixture of methyl alcohol and benzene as rhombic plates, m.p. 218° with effervescence. (Found: Cl, 35.54. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 35.53 per cent.).

It is soluble in acetic acid, acetone, alcohols and ether, insoluble in benzene, toluene and petrol. The alcoholic solution of the substance gave an intense violet coloration with ferric chloride.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 160° . (Found: Cl, 27.92. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 27.74 per cent.).

The sulphuric acid mother-liquor, when evaporated further and cooled, deposited long silky crystals of sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid.

Lactone of 4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl-1- α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzene (II) and *4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl- α -hydroxy- $\omega\omega$ -dichlorostyrene* (III).—The crude product (A) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid. The solution deposited on keeping for a day a small quantity of the substance (II). The mother-liquor (B) was worked up separately (see below). The substance (II) was first crystallised from a mixture of ether and petrol and then for

analysis from acetone as lustrous plates, m.p. 340° (decomp). (Found: Cl, 37.77. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 37.80 per cent.). The substance does not give a violet coloration with ferric chloride. It is soluble in ether, sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid, acetone and insoluble in petrol.

The substance (II) was prepared in quantity thus:—

The substance (I), m.p. 218° (5 g.), was heated in a sulphuric acid bath at about $220-23^{\circ}$. When the effervescence was over, the fused mass was cooled and heated with glacial acetic acid, when a white crystalline powder was obtained. Recrystallised from acetone; m.p. 340° (decomp.).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 315° . (Found: Cl, 32.86. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl_3$ requires Cl, 32.91 per cent.).

The acetic acid mother-liquor (B) was diluted with water till a white turbidity was obtained which dissolved on heating. On cooling a non-crystallisable mass separated as an oil which solidified on keeping. Schleussner and Voswinkel (*loc. cit.*) also found that an oily substance of varying composition was obtained on dilution with water.

The filtrate on further diluting with water deposited a light powder (III). It was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petrol and then from methyl alcohol for analysis, m.p. 165° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 27.08. $C_{10}H_8O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 26.96 per cent.). It is soluble in acetic acid, acetone, ether, alcohols; insoluble in petrol and benzene. The alcoholic solution gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride.

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. $216-17^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 20.48. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6Cl_2$ requires Cl, 20.46 per cent.).

The remaining mother-liquor on evaporation to a small bulk, yielded a small quantity of the substance (I).

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methylmandelic Acid (IV).—The trichloroethylbenzene (I), m.p. 218° (10 g.), was heated on a water-bath with sodium hydroxide (200 c.c. of 10 per cent.) for three hours. A yellowish solution was obtained which was filtered and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The filtrate on keeping deposited clusters of yellowish prismatic needles, m.p. $211-12^{\circ}$. The crude acid was purified through its barium salt. The salt was dissolved in water and treated with dilute sulphuric acid. Barium sulphate was

removed and the filtrate gave prismatic crystals, m.p. 227° (efferv.). (Found: equivalent, 113.9; C, 52.97; H, 4.45. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6$ requires equivalent, 113.04; C, 53.10; H, 4.43 per cent.). The *barium* salt crystallises with 4 molecules of water, of which 2 molecules are removed by heating at 115-20°. (Two samples were analysed; Found: Ba, 31.77, 31.74. $C_{10}H_8O_6Ba, 4H_2O$ requires Ba, 31.71 per cent. After heating to constant weight at 115-20°, found: Ba, 33.93, 34.12. $C_{10}H_8O_6Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 34.58 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared in the usual way; it was crystallised from water, m.p. 168-70° (efferv.). It crystallises with 1 molecule of water. (The *hydrated* substance, found: equivalent, 164.3; H_2O , 5.46. $C_{14}H_{14}O_8, H_2O$ requires equivalent, 164.05; H_2O , 5.49 per cent. The *anhydrous* substance, found: equivalent, 154.09. $C_{14}H_{14}O_8$ requires equivalent, 155.05).

The substance (II) on hydrolysing with sodium hydroxide gave the above mandelic acid:—The substance (II, 2 g.) was mixed with sodium hydroxide (60 c.c. of 10 per cent.); it slowly dissolved when heated on the water-bath. The solution was further heated for about three hours, filtered, and acidified with hydrochloric acid when a yellowish crystalline powder separated. The acid was purified by preparing its barium salt. The mixed melting point of the acid with the mandelic acid described above was 227° (efferv.).

α-Coccinic Acid (V).—The mandelic acid (IV, 1 g.) was dissolved in just sufficient potassium hydroxide solution (20 per cent.). Potassium permanganate (1 g. in 30 c.c. water) solution was added slowly. The mixture was heated for half an hour on the water-bath. The precipitated manganese oxide was filtered off; the filtrate was concentrated and acidified. The acid came down as a white precipitate which was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 316-18° (decomp.). The mixed melting point with Meldrum and Alimchandanani's *α-coccinic acid* was 318°.

The same acid was also obtained by the oxidation of the substance (I). The substance (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (20 c.c. of 10 per cent.) and heated on a water-bath for about 3 hours after which more sodium hydroxide (15 c.c.) was added. Potassium permanganate (0.75 g. in 25 c.c. water) was added slowly and the mixture heated on the water-bath for about two hours. After the removal of manganese oxide, the filtrate was reduced to a small bulk and acidified. The substance on crystallisation was found to be identical with the *α-coccinic acid* already obtained.

2-Methyl-5-carboxy-4-hydroxy-1-ββ-dichloroethylbenzene (VI).—To the hot solution of the substance (I, 10 g.) in acetic acid (40 c.c.), zinc dust (4-5 g.) was added little by little ; the mixture was boiled slightly. After the reaction was over, the mixture was filtered and filtrate diluted with water, when a white light substance separated. It was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from dilute ethyl alcohol ; soft silky needles, m. p. 206°. (Found: Cl, 28·51. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3Cl_2$ requires Cl, 28·47 per cent.).

The same substance was obtained from the substance (II) by subjecting it to reduction with zinc and acetic acid. The substance (II) was suspended in hot glacial acetic acid. On adding zinc dust, as the reaction proceeded, it dissolved. As before, the reduction product was obtained by adding water to the filtrate. The product on crystallisation was found to be identical with the reduction product described above.

Further, the acetyl derivative of the substance (II) was similarly reduced by means of zinc and acetic acid. The reduction product was found to be identical with (VI).

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 170°. (Found: Cl, 24·04. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24·37 per cent.).

The *methyl* derivative was prepared in the usual way by means of dimethyl sulphate. During the course of methylation, the temperature was not allowed to rise above 45°. The methylated product was found to be identical in every respect with that of Meldrum and Alimchandani (*loc. cit.*).

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methylphenylacetic Acid (VII).—The dichloroethylbenzene (VI, 5 g.) was heated with conc. sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) on a water-bath when hydrochloric acid was evolved. After the reaction was over, the cooled mixture was poured into water, when a white substance separated. The crude acid was purified by preparing its barium salt which on acidifying with hydrochloric acid gave the phenylacetic acid as needles. It was crystallised from water in which it is sparingly soluble, m.p. 251°. (Found: equivalent, 105·7. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires equivalent, 105·04).

The *barium* salt crystallises with 2 molecules of water, of which one is removed by heating at 115-20°. (Found: Ba, 35·96. $C_{10}H_8O_5 Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 36·02 per cent. after heating to constant weight at 115-120°, found: Ba, 37·75. $C_{10}H_8O_5 Ba, 1H_2O$ requires Ba, 37·81 per cent.).

The *methyl* derivative was prepared in the usual manner by means of dimethyl sulphate and was found to be identical with that of Meldrum and Alimchandani (*loc. cit.*).

4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl- ω -chlorostyrene (VIII).—If the temperature is allowed to rise during the methylation of the substance (VI), a white powder begins to separate. It was found to be a sodium salt, which on acidifying gave the substance (VIII). It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as double pyramids, m.p. 163°. (Found: Cl, 15.71. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 15.65 per cent.). The substance did not give a violet coloration with ferric chloride.

The same substance was prepared from the methyl derivative of the substance (VI). The derivative (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (20 c.c. of 20 per cent.). On heating, the sparingly soluble sodium salt began to separate, which on acidification yielded the substance, m.p. 163°.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl-1-ethylbenzene (IX).—To the hot solution of the substance (III) in acetic acid, zinc dust was added in small quantity at a time. Vigorous reaction took place. The mixture was boiled, filtered and the filtrate diluted with water. The reduction product was crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 315° (decomp.). (Found: equivalent, 180.0; C, 66.08; H, 6.83. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires equivalent, 180.1; C, 66.63; H, 6.72 per cent.).

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methyl-1- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzene (X).—*m*-Cresotic acid (15 g.), chloral hydrate (27 g.) and sulphuric acid (120 c.c.) were mixed together. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into the solution for about 3 hours. On the third day, the mixture was poured over ice. A white precipitate was obtained, which was dried and dissolved in glacial acetic acid: rectangular plates, recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 227-28° (efferv.). (Found: Cl, 44.20. $C_{10}H_8O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 44.60 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from toluene and then from alcohol, m.p. 197°. (Found: Cl, 39.32. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4Cl_4$ requires Cl, 39.40 per cent.)

The substance (X, 5 g.) was boiled for an hour with potassium hydroxide (100 c.c. of 20 per cent.). On acidifying the solution, a small quantity of a dark substance separated, which was removed; the filtrate deposited a crystalline powder, which was purified by preparing its barium salt. After removing barium as barium sul-

phate, the acid obtained was found to be identical with the mandelic acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the substance (I).

The tetrachloroethylbenzene (X) was reduced by means of zinc and acetic acid as before. The reduction product was similarly obtained and found to be identical with that got by the reduction of the substance (I).

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